

A Computational Method for Solving Fractional Optimal Control Problems Arising in Cancer Treatment

Sedigheh Sabermahani^{1,*}, Yadollah Ordokhani^{1,†}

¹ Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Mathematical Sciences, Alzahra University, Tehran, Iran

Abstract. The main aim of this study is to present a computational method based on Fibonacci polynomials for solving fractional nonlinear optimal control problems, where this scheme is applied to solving the optimal control problems of cancer treatment. Here, a pseudo-operational matrix of fractional integration is presented for the considered polynomials. Then, we use this matrix, the Gaussian quadrature rule, and the collocation method to reduce the given problem into a system of algebraic equations. The effectiveness of the present technique is tested by means of one example and the results confirm its good performance.

Keywords: Fibonacci polynomials, Pseudo-operational matrix, collocation method, cancer, Optimal control problem.

1. Introduction

In recent years, an optimal control strategy was presented for tumor burden under immune suppression with a description in Caputo fractional derivative sense. The following cancer model describes the interactions between the tumor cells $T(t)$, immune cells $I(t)$, normal cells $N(t)$, and fat cells $F(t)$ at time t near tumor site, while chemotherapeutic drugs $D(t)$ is injected into the body [1]:

$$\text{Min } \mathfrak{J} = \int_0^1 [\omega_1 T(t) - \omega_2 N(t) + \omega_3 u^2(t)] dt, \quad (1)$$

subject to

$$\begin{aligned} {}_0^c D_t^\alpha T(t) &= r_1 T(t) (1 - p_1 T(t)) - a_1 T(t) I(t) - a_2 T(t) N(t) + c_1 T(t) F(t) - \gamma_1 D(t) T(t), \\ {}_0^c D_t^\alpha I(t) &= s_1 + b_1 \frac{T(t) I(t)}{h + T(t)} - a_3 T(t) I(t) - \mu_1 I(t) - \gamma_2 D(t) I(t), \\ {}_0^c D_t^\alpha N(t) &= r_2 N(t) (1 - p_2 N(t)) - a_4 T(t) N(t) - \gamma_3 D(t) N(t), \\ {}_0^c D_t^\alpha F(t) &= r_3 F(t) (1 - p_3 F(t)) - a_5 T(t) F(t) - \gamma_4 D(t) F(t), \\ {}_0^c D_t^\alpha D(t) &= u(t) - \zeta D(t), \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

and

$$T(0) = T_0, \quad I(0) = I_0, \quad N(0) = N_0, \quad F(0) = F_0, \quad D(0) = D_0,$$

*Speaker. E-mail address: s.saber@alzahra.ac.ir

†Corresponding author. E-mail address: ordokhani@alzahra.ac.ir .

where $u(t)$ stands for the dose of the chemotherapeutic drug. This model was solved by some numerical methods such as generalized shifted Legendre polynomials [2]. Here, we propose a new numerical algorithm to solve the mentioned cancer model based on Fibonacci polynomials and collocation method.

2. Fibonacci polynomials and their properties

Fibonacci polynomials are defined as the following form [3]

$$F_m(x) = \sum_{i=0}^{\lfloor m/2 \rfloor} \binom{m-i}{i} x^{m-2i}, \quad m \geq 0. \quad (3)$$

Here, the first M -terms of the Fibonacci polynomials are used to propose an approximation. Then, an arbitrary function $x(t) \in L^2[0, 1]$ may be approximated as follows

$$x(t) \approx \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} x_j F_j(t) = X^T \Psi(t), \quad (4)$$

subject to

$$X = [x_0, x_1, \dots, x_{M-1}]^T, \quad \Psi(t) = [F_0(t), F_1(t), \dots, F_{M-1}(t)]^T. \quad (5)$$

The coefficient vector $X = (x_j)$ is given by $X^T = \Delta^T D^{-1}$, where $D = \langle \Psi, \Psi \rangle$, $\Delta = \langle x, \Psi \rangle$.

2.1. Riemann-Liouville pseudo-operational matrix and Fibonacci polynomials

This subsection is devoted to construct the Riemann-Liouville pseudo-operational matrix for Fibonacci polynomials. The Riemann-Liouville integration of the vector $\Psi(t)$ can be expressed by

$${}_0 I^\alpha \Psi(t) \approx P(\alpha, t) \Psi(t). \quad (6)$$

$P(\alpha, t) = t^\alpha p_\alpha$ is the $M \times M$ pseudo-operational matrix of Riemann-Liouville fractional integration. Now, we obtain this matrix. Using Eq. (3) and considering the properties of Riemann-Liouville fractional integral, we have

$$\begin{aligned} {}_0 I^\alpha F_m(t) &= \sum_{i=0}^{\lfloor m/2 \rfloor} \binom{m-i}{i} {}_0 I^\alpha t^{m-2i} \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^{\lfloor m/2 \rfloor} \binom{m-i}{i} \eta_{m-2i+\alpha}(t), \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where

$$\eta_{m-2i+\alpha}(t) = \frac{\Gamma(m-2i+1)}{\Gamma(m-2i+1+\alpha)} t^{m-2i+\alpha},$$

and $m \geq 0$. Then, we have

$${}_0 I^\alpha F_m(t) = t^\alpha \tilde{\eta}_{m-2i+\alpha}(t)$$

where

$$\tilde{\eta}_{m-2i+\alpha}(t) = \sum_{i=0}^{\lfloor m/2 \rfloor} \binom{m-i}{i} \frac{\Gamma(m-2i+1)}{\Gamma(m-2i+1+\alpha)} t^{m-2i}.$$

Now, by expanding $\tilde{\eta}_{m-2i+\alpha}(t)$ regarding Fibonacci polynomials, we have

$$\tilde{\eta}_{m-2i+\alpha}(t) \approx \phi_{m,\alpha}^T \Psi(t), \quad (8)$$

Then, we achieve the following relation:

$$p_\alpha = [\phi_{m,\alpha}^T], \quad m = 0, 1, \dots, M-1.$$

3. Numerical method

Here, we discuss the approximate solution of the considered model in Eqs. (1)-(2), by applying the Riemann-Liouville pseudo-operational matrix of Fibonacci polynomials. For this aim, we approximate the following functions by the Fibonacci polynomials.

$$\begin{aligned} {}_0^c D_t^\alpha T(t) &\approx \mathfrak{I}^T \Psi(t), & {}_0^c D_t^\alpha I(t) &\approx \mathfrak{J}^T \Psi(t), \\ {}_0^c D_t^\alpha N(t) &\approx \mathfrak{N}^T \Psi(t), & {}_0^c D_t^\alpha F(t) &\approx \mathfrak{F}^T \Psi(t), \\ {}_0^c D_t^\alpha D(t) &\approx \mathfrak{D}^T \Psi(t), & u(t) &\approx \mathfrak{U}^T \Psi(t) \triangleq u_M(t). \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Next, due to the initial conditions in Eq. (2) and by implementing Riemann-Liouville pseudo-operational matrix, we get

$$\begin{aligned} T(t) &\approx \mathfrak{I}^T P(\alpha, t) \Psi(t) + T_0 \triangleq T_M(t), \\ I(t) &\approx \mathfrak{J}^T P(\alpha, t) \Psi(t) + I_0 \triangleq I_M(t), \\ N(t) &\approx \mathfrak{N}^T P(\alpha, t) \Psi(t) + N_0 \triangleq N_M(t), \\ F(t) &\approx \mathfrak{F}^T P(\alpha, t) \Psi(t) + F_0 \triangleq F_M(t), \\ D(t) &\approx \mathfrak{D}^T P(\alpha, t) \Psi(t) + D_0 \triangleq D_M(t). \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Inserting the above approximations into Eq. (1) yields the following approximation for the performance index

$$\mathfrak{J}_M = \int_0^1 [\omega_1 T_M(t) - \omega_2 N_M(t) + \omega_3 u_M^2(t)] dt, \quad (11)$$

the value of the above integral can be approximated by using an \mathcal{N} -point Gauss-Legendre quadrature rule and we name the value of this $\hat{\mathfrak{J}}$. Also, by substituting Eqs. (9)-(10) into Eq. (2), we have

$$y_1(t) \triangleq \mathfrak{I}^T \Psi(t) - \left(r_1 T_M(t) (1 - p_1 T_M(t)) - a_1 T_M(t) I_M(t) - a_2 T_M(t) N_M(t) + c_1 T_M(t) F_M(t) - \gamma_1 D_M(t) T_M(t) \right),$$

$$y_2(t) \triangleq \mathfrak{J}^T \Psi(t) - \left(s_1 + b_1 \frac{T_M(t) I_M(t)}{h + T_M(t)} - a_3 T_M(t) I_M(t) - \mu_1 I_M(t) - \gamma_2 D_M(t) I_M(t) \right),$$

$$y_3(t) \triangleq \mathfrak{N}^T \Psi(t) - \left(r_2 N_M(t) (1 - p_2 N(t)) - a_4 T_M(t) N_M(t) - \gamma_3 D(t) N(t) \right),$$

$$y_4(t) \triangleq \mathfrak{F}^T \Psi(t) - \left(r_3 F_M(t) (1 - p_3 F_M(t)) - a_5 T_M(t) F_M(t) - \gamma_4 D_M(t) F_M(t) \right),$$

$$y_5(t) \triangleq \mathfrak{D}^T \Psi(t) - \left(u_M(t) - \zeta D_M(t) \right).$$

As the next step, by taking the collocation points $t_i = \frac{i}{M-1}, i = 0, 1, \dots, M-1$ into the above equations, we obtain a system of algebraic equations, and then, we have $\Omega_j = y_j(t_i) = 0, j = 0, 1, \dots, 5$. Therefore, we achieve

$$\mathfrak{J}^* = \hat{\mathfrak{J}} + \sum_{i=1}^5 \Omega_i \lambda_i,$$

where, $\Omega_i = [\Omega_{i,0}, \dots, \Omega_{i,M-1}]$ and $\lambda_i = [\lambda_{i,0}, \dots, \lambda_{i,M-1}]^T$ and they are the Lagrange multipliers. The necessary conditions for the extremum of the mentioned functional are given by

$$\frac{\partial \mathfrak{J}^*}{\partial \mathfrak{I}} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \mathfrak{J}^*}{\partial \mathfrak{J}} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \mathfrak{J}^*}{\partial \mathfrak{N}} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \mathfrak{J}^*}{\partial \mathfrak{F}} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \mathfrak{J}^*}{\partial \mathfrak{D}} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \mathfrak{J}^*}{\partial \mathfrak{U}} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \mathfrak{J}^*}{\partial \lambda_i} = 0.$$

4. Numerical simulation

In this section, we consider the model cancer-obesity interaction given in Eqs. (1)-(2). We consider the values of the weights as $\omega_1 = 20, \omega_2 = 1$ and $\omega_3 = 1$. The values of the parameters are given in Table 1. The main aim of this example is minimizing J . For this approach, we

Table 1. Values of the parameters for the cancer model [2]

Parameters	Description	Units	Estimate value
r_1	Growth rate of tumor cells	day^{-1}	1.5
p_1	Reciprocal carrying capacity of tumor cells	$cells^{-1}$	1
a_1	Competition term of tumor cells with immune cells	$cells^{-1}day^{-1}$	0.5
a_2	Competition term of tumor cells with normal cells	$cells^{-1}day^{-1}$	1
c_1	Competition term of fat cells with tumor cells	$cells^{-1}day^{-1}$	1.5
γ_1	Response of tumor cells to chemotherapeutic drug	day^{-1}	0.08
s_1	Immune source rate	$cellsday^{-1}$	0.33
b_1	Recruitment rate of immune cells by tumor cells	day^{-1}	0.01
h	Immune response stimulated by tumor cells	$cells^2$	0.3
a_3	Competition term of immune cells with tumor cells	$cells^{-1}day^{-1}$	0.5
μ_1	Death rate of immune cells	day^{-1}	0.2
γ_2	Response of immune cells to immunotherapeutic drug	day^{-1}	2×10^{-11}
r_2	Growth rate of normal cells	day^{-1}	1
p_2	Reciprocal carrying capacity of normal cells	$cells^{-1}$	1
a_4	Competition term of immune cells with tumor cells	$cells^{-1}day$	1
γ_3	Response of normal cells to chemotherapeutic drug	day^{-1}	0.008
r_3	Growth rate of fat cells	day^{-1}	0.75
p_3	Reciprocal carrying capacity of fat cells	$cells^{-1}$	1.5
a_5	Competition term of fat cells with tumor cells	$cells^{-1}day$	0.1
γ_4	Response of fat cells to chemotherapeutic drug	day^{-1}	0.008
ζ	Decay rate of D	day^{-1}	0.1

consider $T_0 = 1, I_0 = 0.001, N_0 = 4, F_0 = 0.25$ and $D_0 = 0.5$ and by implementing the suggested method, we obtain the numerical solution of the considered model in Eqs. (1)-(2) with $\alpha = 1$, and 0.95. The approximate solutions of tumor cells $T(t)$, immune cells $I(t)$, normal cells $N(t)$, fat cells $F(t)$, drug $D(t)$, and control $u(t)$ are displayed in Fig. 1. For more investigation, we show the residual errors $y_1(t), y_2(t), y_3(t), y_4(t)$, and $y_5(t)$ in Fig. 2. As it can be seen from Fig. 1 in both cases, the tumor population decreases and the normal cell population is renewed. Also, the immune cell population approaches and the number of fat cells increases over time. Moreover, after eradicating most of the tumor population, the drug concentration $D(t)$ and dose $u(t)$ decrease.

5. Conclusion

A numerical method based on Fibonacci polynomials was proposed to solve a class of fractional optimal control problems (FOCPs) arising in cancer treatment. In this model, the interactions between tumor cells, normal cells, fat cells, and immune cells together with chemotherapeutic drug concentration were included. To design the computational method, we presented a

Fig. 1. Tumor cells $T(t)$, immune cells $I(t)$, normal cells $N(t)$, fat cells $F(t)$, drug $D(t)$, and control $u(t)$ for $\alpha = 1$ (top) and $\alpha = 0.95$ (down).

Fig. 2. Plot of residual errors $y_1(t), y_2(t), y_3(t), y_4(t)$, and $y_5(t)$, for $\alpha = 1$ (top) and $\alpha = 0.95$ (down).

new Riemann-Liouville pseudo-operational matrix for Fibonacci polynomials. Then, the mentioned matrix with the help of the collocation method was employed to convert the considered problem into a system of algebraic equations. The numerical algorithm presented here can be explored in new topics involving fractional differential equations and FOCPs.

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